

Cobalt(II) Complexes with some Substituted Quinolines

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Cobalt chloride, bromide and perchlorate were reacted in ethanolic medium with some substituted quinolines(L) and complexes having the general formula CoL_2X_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) and $\text{L}=2\text{-Chloroquinoline}$, 3-bromoquinoline and $5:6\text{-Benzoquinoline}$ and $[\text{CoL}_6]/\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{ClO}_4$ & $\text{L}=2\text{-Chloroquinoline}$) were isolated. The magnetic moments and electronic spectral measurements clearly show that the dihalo complexes with 3-bromoquinoline and the perchlorato complex with 2-chloroquinoline are octahedral and all other complexes are tetrahedral. The i. r. spectrum of the perchlorate complex reveals only one band at 1100 cm^{-1} indicating that the perchlorate group is ionic and a large value for Λ_M is in conformity with this.

LIGAND field theory predicts that the ions most likely to form regular tetrahedral complexes are those having a spherically symmetrical non-bonding shell in this environment^{1,2}. In addition to the crystal field effects, the ligand properties like size, shape, polarisability of the ligands, π acceptor capacity may have great influence in determining the relative stabilities of the tetrahedral and octahedral configurations. Cobalt(II) ion has a $(e_g)^4 (t_{2g})^3$ configuration and regular tetrahedral symmetry is more common, in case of Cobalt(II) complexes. Many tetra-, penta-, and hexa-coordinated complexes of Cobalt(II) have been reported³⁻⁷ in the literature. In this communication some Cobalt(II) complexes with some substituted quinolines are reported.

Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used were of AR grade. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal and halogen (ionisable). The conductance measurements were carried out using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge of the type CLO102 and a dip type cell. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens using Gouy method. The infrared spectra on nujol mulls were recorded using Unicam SP200 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP500 spectrophotometer using $M/100$ dimethylformamide solutions and also nujol mulls.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution of the hydrated metal halide or perchlorate and the respective ligands in stoichiometric ratio for about 2 hours and then allowing the resulting solution to stand for about 2 to 3 days.

Analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds, excepting the perchlorate complex, reported in this work are non-electrolytes in dimethylformamide medium as indicated by their low values of molar conductance. (Table 1). But a high value of 87.9 mhos for Λ_M in case of the perchlorate complex suggests that it is a 2:1 electrolyte indicating that perchlorate group is ionic but not coordinated. All the complexes reported in this work are spin free complexes with high magnetic moments, μ_{eff} values ranging between 4.36 and 5.12 B.M. indicating the presence of three unpaired electrons. The infra-red spectra of the ligands and the complexes show that the ligands are bonded to the metal. A broad band at about 1100 cm^{-1} in case of the perchlorate complex definitely indicates that the perchlorate group is ionic.

The electronic spectra and the magnetic moments show clearly that the complexes reported now can be classified into those of octahedral or tetrahedral stereochemistry.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(II) COMPLEXES WITH SOME SUBSTITUTED QUINOLINES

Compound	%Cobalt		%Halogen		Conductance Λ_M (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectral bands. $\lambda_{\text{max}}\text{ cm}^{-1}(\epsilon)$
	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.			
1. $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{BQ})_2$	11.85	12.07	14.40	14.52	0.2	4.36	16000 (195), 14820 (198)
2. $\text{CoBr}_2(\text{BQ})_2$	9.98	10.21	27.36	27.69	4.3	4.54	16000 (170), 14820 (195)
3. $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{ClQ})_2$	12.72	12.90	15.16	15.52	0.8	4.76	16000 (195), 14820 (172)
4. $\text{CoBr}_2(\text{ClQ})_2$	10.58	10.90	28.72	29.29	3.2	4.57	15380 (170)
5. $[\text{Co}(\text{ClQ})_6](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	4.81	4.77	—	—	87.9	5.12	19050 (41)
6. $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{BrQ})_2$	10.59	10.80	12.62	12.99	4.2	4.99	19420 (51), 17100 (52)
7. $\text{CoBr}_2(\text{BrQ})_2$	9.00	9.28	24.57	25.18	4.3	5.12	19420 (53), 16660 (50)

BQ=5:6 Benzoquinoline, ClQ=2-Chloroquinoline, BrQ=3-Bromo quinoline.

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Octahedral Complexes

The complexes $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{BrQ})_2$ and $\text{CoBr}_2(\text{Br.Q})_2$ have very high melting points and are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents. They have high magnetic moments (4.99 and 5.12 B.M.) typical of octahedral cobalt(II) complex⁸. In their solid and solution electronic spectra, they exhibit two absorption bands at about $20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $17,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Cobalt(II) complexes in the octahedral environment should have three spin allowed d-d transitions⁹. The band at $\sim 20,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to the ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P}) (\nu_3)$ and at $\sim 17,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\nu_2)$ transition. These spectra are very much similar to that of violet isomer¹⁰ of CoCl_2Py_2 and that¹¹ of $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{Br.Py})_2$ which were reported to be octahedral in nature. The poor solubility, high melting point, characteristic magnetic moments and electronic spectral bands clearly indicate a polymeric octahedral structure for these complexes presumably with halogen bridging. The presence of halogen bridges could not be indicated by the i.r. spectra due to limitation of the range of the instrument used.

The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{ClQ})_6] (\text{ClO}_4)_2$ has magnetic moment and electronic spectrum typical of octahedral complexes as discussed above. Further, ionic nature of the perchlorate group was indicated by i r. spectrum (broad band at 1100 cm^{-1}) and also by high molar conductance (87.9 mhos).

Tetrahedral Complexes

All other Cobalt(II) complexes investigated in this work have magnetic moments between 4.36 and 4.76 B.M. typical of tetrahedral¹² Complexes. The electronic spectra of these complexes show very intense bands with large values for extinction co-efficients ϵ (as compared to low values for octahedral configuration)

near about $14000\text{-}16000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ similar to that observed in tetrahedral¹³ $\text{CoCl}_2 (2 \text{ MIZ})_2$ complex. The bands can be assigned to ${}^4\text{A}_2 - {}^4\text{T}_1\text{P}$ transition.

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